
TOLERANCE AS A THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL ASPECT IN TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract.

The education of tolerance among students is one of the most important tasks of teachers of higher education, since with the beginning of education at a technical university; young people begin to communicate with people of a different faith, different culture and other outlooks on life. This article deals with the problem of interethnic tolerance and considers tolerance as a theoretical and methodological aspect in a foreign language teaching.

Keywords.

Tolerance, sociocultural interaction, psychological development mutual understanding, a foreign language.

Introduction:

Teachers as moderators and facilitators of the educational process educate students in the spirit of mutual respect and national tolerance, since students are among the most progressive, organized, intellectually and creatively developed part of the youth, and since future graduates, in the presence of diverse socio-cultural and professional interactions, will establish contacts with foreign partners. The teacher participates in the process of improving the worldview of students, expanding the horizons of their worldview, develops their reflection, and promotes self-awareness as carriers of social values, subjects of sociocultural interaction and a person useful to society [27,1800]. With this in mind, the teacher needs to design didactic situations for the development of dialogical communication, create conditions for personal self-realization in the classroom and provide students with the opportunity to defend their own opinion, freely express their views and their life position. The components of tolerance, namely: the ability for interpersonal perception and evaluation of people, the ability for socio-psychological adaptation in various situations, the ability to get in touch with different people, win them

over, achieve mutual understanding are of great importance for the psychological development of students, their socialization and their acquisition of forms of social behavior.

Main part:

The concept of "tolerance" has two main dimensions: sustainability and tolerance. Stability is characterized by a sequence of actions of the individual and manifests itself as the ability to self-govern. Tolerance is one of the characteristics of a person, which manifests itself when the views, opinions, behavior of other people do not coincide with the opinions and assessments of this person, and which manifests itself in its stability. The term tolerance can also be understood as the art of living next to the other [18,275].

Teaching a foreign language, based on the use of professionally oriented authentic material, helps to familiarize students with the culture of the country of the language being studied, reflects the psycholinguistic features of native speakers, the subtleties of their mental make-up and cultures, motivates the student through the content and ways of expressing it to active educational and practical activities and raises the level tolerance of students, which contributes to the effectiveness of interpersonal and intercultural interaction by means of a foreign language using the students' own cultural experience. The use of modern teaching technologies, primarily interactive and interactive, contributes to the creation of an emotionally balanced, comfortable psychological atmosphere within a multi-ethnic student group, the involvement of students in cognitive creative activity, the development of critical thinking, tolerance, activity, and self-discipline.

The ability to independently reflect on new socio-economic demands and manage one's own development taking them into account is an indicator of the level of development of a person's tolerance. The greatest effectiveness of educating professional tolerance among students in the process of teaching a foreign language is achieved if the teacher provides students with the opportunity to show their independence and responsible freedom in solving issues when communicating in a foreign language, if a favorable moral and psychological atmosphere is created in the audience, conditions for creativity and meaningful learning, curiosity and cognitive motives of trainees are activated and stimulated. Such an organization of the educational space contributes to the training of specialists who are in demand by the modern social order, tolerant, flexible, able to adapt quickly to a changing situation in communication, able to maintain composure in conditions of uncertainty and absolute ambiguity.

The system of learning activities organized by the teacher, the use of innovative and alternative educational technologies based on the use of business, simulation, role-playing and other games, the situational nature and emotionality of learning provide an intensification of the acquisition of tolerance components by students [17,3518]. The use of problem situations, elements of socio-psychological training, the implementation of practical tasks of a creative nature that pose cognitive tasks for students and create a problem-project situation, linguistic and regional information motivate students to professional communication in a foreign language.

In the educational process, we should focus on three interrelated and interdependent aspects of educational activity:

- Students mastering the skills of self-control, self-assessment, self-analysis;
- Mastery of foreign language communication with the recognition of the equality of all participants in communication;
- The ability to cope with stressful situations caused by the actions of individuals from the immediate environment of students. Therefore, in our opinion, teachers need to consistently educate students in tolerance, develop their ability for self-government, self-regulation, self-correction and continuous self-improvement.

The specifics of the process of teaching a foreign language are determined by the principles of teaching, among which the following principles are of the most importance:

- The principle of dividing activity into separate significant micro situations, which allows the teacher to organize a system of exercises that allow students to realize the strategy of their tolerant behavior in this context;
- The principle of high communicativeness, active involvement of students in situations of interpersonal interaction in compliance with the ethics of foreign language communication;
- The principle of taking into account the mental, social and linguistic and cultural characteristics of the countries of the language being studied and their correlation with the Uzbek/Russian, socio-cultural space. The factors influencing the effectiveness of educating technical university students of professional tolerance when teaching foreign language communication include:
 - Psychological factor
 - Mental properties, states of students;
 - Socio-psychological factor

- The nature of the relationship in the study group, between students and teachers, the moral and psychological atmosphere prevailing in the group, students' interest in learning or indifference to it;

- Pedagogical factor - the teacher's understanding of the importance of educating such a personality quality as tolerance in teaching a foreign language.

The educational potential during a foreign language lesson is manifested in the following activities:

- in the development of a personal unique opinion of each student;

- in the ability of students studying a foreign language to correlate different points of view, while showing their tolerance;

- in improving the communicative skills of trainees, which facilitates the socialization and adaptation of young people to life, to the conditions of their future professional activities.

An important factor in educating students of professional tolerance is the effective management of the study group in order to develop a common opinion [10,133]. To do this, the teacher needs adequate information about the interests and needs of students, about the carriers of a negative opinion in the student group and the reasons for its occurrence. The high professionalism and authority of the teacher, the scientific organization of the educational process, the resolution of conflict situations through group discussions or, if necessary, narrow conversations, etc. are also mandatory. The process of teaching a foreign language with the parallel task of educating tolerance must be carried out on the basis of the use of authentic teaching materials. Original materials retain their true value in natural communicative situations. The task of the teacher is to give a purposeful nature to the abundance of diverse original material and find ways to present it to students in order to solve the set educational and educational tasks and to increase the level of tolerance [41, 2088].

Conclusion:

Thus, in the educational process of teaching a foreign language, the development of students' personal qualities, an increase in their tolerance level through social status relations, through role relationships, through joint activities, through moral relationships, which are modeled in various forms of educational space, take place.

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